

Summary

During the year 2021-2023, Norwegian rescue services in northern Norway used a variety of mapping platforms of digital maps, the majority of which do not cater to search-and-rescue (SAR) actions and are not interoperable. Maps are used as information and decision support tools for action planning, after-action assessments, communication and coordination, safe navigation, and situational awareness.

The use of maps differs per the needs of responders, timing and location, the availability of functionalities, and the availability of information. Due to the whereabouts of a SAR effort, certain functions of mapping platforms can be inapplicable, affecting the operational needs.

Furthermore, SAR practices are influenced by the availability and quality of information integration functions on digital mapping platforms. The use of maps should be analysed and enhanced with attention to where, how, and when they are practised, integrating context-specific functions and information.

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Key Messages

- ⇒ The response capacity of SAR units is impacted by the availability of effective mapping solutions, especially in remote areas of northern Norway, where live tracking can increase resource connectivity, situational awareness, SAR strategy adaptability, and reduce response time.
- ⇒ When in use by rescue services, the functionality of digital maps relies on infrastructure, organisational practices, and relevant legislation, which in turn affects search practices, motivation, and involvement.
- ⇒ Beyond practitioner expertise, the effectiveness of employing digital maps in SAR efforts depends on coherent legislation, timely integration of information, reliable funding, and catered technological solutions.
- ⇒ Digital maps are a joint effort, and they stimulate cooperation on several scales: during a SAR incident response, outside the incident between rescue services, and between rescue services and institutions providing mapping services.
- ⇒ While the attention to the role of maps and their functionality is gaining traction, adjustments to the employment of maps by Norwegian rescue services should be implemented with care of where, how, and when the maps are used.

For more information, contact:

Virga Popovaitė, Visiting Researcher at the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Lapland
virga.popovaitė@ulapland.fi

Background

Northern Norway spans the Arctic and sub-Arctic, where weather conditions, sparsely populated areas, difficult terrain, and large bodies of water can become threatening to those venturing outside. To mitigate outcomes of any accidents, Norway has a well-established network of rescue services which participate in search-and-rescue (SAR) operations. These operations fall outside of regular first responders' responsibilities and are managed either by the Joint Rescue Coordination Centre or by the local police in cooperation with public, private, and volunteer sectors (Justis- og beredskapsdepartementet, 2018).

In addition to timely response, rescuers also need to be mindful of their equipment which can be affected by cold or by infrastructural challenges specific to the area (Albrechtsen & Indreiten, 2021; Ryghaug et al. 2022). Difficult operational settings require good collaboration between rescue parties. However, participating parties can have different interests and practices, which can be hard to integrate into the collaborative effort (Andreassen et al., 2018). With technological advancement, digital maps partake a more active role in SAR action coordination. They are used for decision making, information communication, and shared situational awareness. Maps significantly interlink with the response capacity of Norwegian rescue services and have the potential to hamper or enhance a collaborative rescue action.

Digital mapping solutions relate to infrastructure, organisational practices, and legislation

When rescue services use maps, a variety of factors affect how well they work, such as infrastructure and legislation. For maps to be effective, there need to be things like radio towers, satellites, electricity, and proper equipment. On top of that, organisations need to train rescue workers on how to use the maps and find funding to buy the software and hardware needed. In addition to skills in operating mapping solutions, funding issues or legislative decisions can restrict access to digital mapping solutions or relevant information (Popovaitè 2023a). However, it is not only about training, legislations or available tools.

The success of these maps depends on where and when they are used. For example, other technologies or changes in the landscape can disrupt the efficiency of maps (Popovaitè 2023b; Popovaitè 2023c). As digital maps influence SAR practices, they are more than merely visual representations. By sharing their location, rescue teams can see the bigger picture, which helps them work better and boosts the motivation of responders in the field (Popovaitè 2023a). Thus, to understand the full impact of digital maps, it is important to analyse how, where and when they are used.

Digital maps can both strengthen or weaken the response capacity

With some mapping solutions, responders can immediately share their observations, planned search areas, and tracks as the SAR effort proceeds. This enables rescuers in the field to connect with those who have expertise in SAR effort management but are further away (Popovaitè 2023a). The feature is

especially important in remote areas where local resources can be limited, as it can strengthen the response capacity of remote communities. Furthermore, being able to share information directly through the mapping platform can save time during the early stages of an operation, as responders do not have to wait for establishing an operation management centre (Popovaité 2023a).

Additionally, maps provide vital information necessary for safe navigation over difficult terrain or around archipelagos (Popovaité 2023b; 2023c). When maps are ready to use before an incident occurs, the reaction time can be shortened. However, digital mapping solutions can also hamper a rescue response. They can miscommunicate the direction of movement, fragment the big picture of the SAR effort, and misrepresent the landscape (Popovaité 2023a; 2023b; 2023c).

Therefore, working with digital maps also prompts sharing expertise and cooperation beyond rescue operations

When responders have unequal skills in working with specific mapping platforms, this can limit the application of maps as a tool. However, this also provides a possibility for collaborations beyond a SAR operation. For example, shared training activities between different volunteer organisations (Popovaité 2023a). Additionally, Arctic landscape (glaciers, glacial rivers) changes faster than it is mapped out. This difference between maps and the terrain requires local institutions in relevant areas to cooperate in collecting additional information to ensure safe navigation (Popovaité 2023c).

Furthermore, mapping out the Norwegian territory is a slow, detailed and costly process. This is especially visible in maritime areas and Svalbard archipelago which at times can be hard to access due to weather conditions (Popovaité 2023b; 2023c). Thus, to acquire high-resolution data, organisations responsible for mapping out the Norwegian territory engage in collaborations. Lastly, mapping services also cooperate with rescue responders. This collaboration enhances the available information through maps, and, in case of the new mapping tool in development, it also influences the possible ways of working with maps.

Norwegian rescue services are changing their practices of working with maps

In 2023, guidelines for the search of missing persons on land were released with a goal to unify and inform SAR practices. Furthermore, the initiative to develop a new mapping platform jointly operable by the Joint Rescue Coordination Centre, police, and volunteer organisations aims to provide a mapping platform for rescue services. In addition to catering to the needs of rescue services, this platform aims to address access and data management issues. It is important to note that the needs of responders vary due to landscape, infrastructure, and organisational practices. Therefore, unified mapping practices and the new mapping solution should be implemented with care to where, when, and how maps are practised by rescue services.

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